

Multiphysics FEM-based Design and Thermo-mechanical Simulation of Domestically Used tuberous food Processing Machine

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ARTICLE INFO

Paper ID: IJASTR-68DC0A2B12066

Received: 2025-09-02

Published: 2025-10-05

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17330588>

Page No: 203-217

ABSTRACT

Tuberous root crops such as yam, cassava, and cocoyam are vital staples in Nigeria, yet their traditional manual processing through pounding is laborious, intensive, time-consuming, and physically demanding. This study applies a Multiphysics finite element method (FEM) approach to the design and thermo-mechanical simulation of a domestically used tuberous food processing machine, with focus on optimizing its processing chamber with the critical site of thermal and structural interactions. The machine comprises a stainless-steel container with shaft-blade assembly and polyethylene insulation for heat retention. Using ANSYS, thermal analyses incorporated internal convection from food heating and external cooling, while static structural simulations evaluated von Mises stress, elastic strain, and total deformation under coupled loads. Mesh models of open and closed chamber designs were refined for accurate predictions. Findings from the study showed that bottom-heated models achieved higher base temperatures of 80.5 °C enabling rapid processing. The heat flux peaked at 0.0186 W/mm² in the localized hotspots but was reduced to 0.0030 W/mm² through design refinements, enhancing uniformity. Equivalent elastic strain, initially 0.0818 mm/mm at chamber-blade interfaces, was minimized to 0.000126 mm/mm after optimization. Similarly, von Mises stress fell from 86.9 MPa in the chamber to 24.3 MPa in blade assemblies, well below the yield strength of stainless steel. The findings demonstrate that FEM-based thermo-mechanical analysis effectively informs material selection and geometry optimization, producing safer, more durable, and energy-efficient machines. Beyond technical performance, adoption of such optimized designs can alleviate manual drudgery, improve food safety, and support food security in agrarian communities.

Keywords: Tuberous food processing machine, Finite element method (FEM), Thermo-mechanical simulation, Multiphysics analysis, Design optimization

Cite This Paper : Alexis Malachy Robert and Victor David Okon (2025). " Multiphysics FEM-based Design and Thermo-mechanical Simulation of Domestically Used tuberous food Processing Machine ". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL RESEARCH (IJASTR)*, vol. 15, no. 5, 2025, pp. 203-217. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17330588>

1. Introduction

Tuberous root crops, such as yam, cassava, and sweet potato, are staple foods in many regions around the world. These crops are typically processed through pounding, a labour-intensive task that requires significant physical effort. To alleviate this burden, the development of tuberous root food-based processing machines has gained attention (Laila et al., 2025; Javed et al., 2025). Nigeria, as a country with a rich agricultural heritage, heavily relies on tuberous root

crops such as yam, cassava, and cocoyam as staple foods. The traditional method of processing these crops involves manually pounding them using a mortar and pestle, which is labour-intensive and time-consuming (Hazarika et al., 2025). This study argues for the adoption and improvement of tuberous root food-based processing machines in Nigeria to enhance food processing efficiency, reduce drudgery, and promote economic growth. Tuberous root crops play a vital role in Nigeria's food security and economic development (Onawo & Egboduku, 2025). However, the traditional method of processing these crops poses several challenges. Manual tuberous food processing requires significant physical effort, leading to fatigue and health issues among women, who are primarily responsible for this task (Ojolo, 2024; Onawo & Egboduku, 2025). Additionally, the process is time-consuming, limiting the quantity of food that can be processed within a given period. These challenges hinder the potential of tuberous root crops to contribute to food security and economic growth. A study conducted by Ogiemudia et al. (2016) found that the use of pounding machines increased processing efficiency by 70% compared to manual pounding. This improvement allows for increased food production, which can help meet the growing demand and reduce post-harvest losses. The physical strain associated with manual processing method can lead to musculoskeletal disorders and other health issues. By introducing pounding machines, the physical burden on women can be alleviated, promoting their well-being. Furthermore, the use of machines reduces the risk of injuries caused by accidents during manual processing of tuberous food (Prasetyo et al., 2022; Sypuła et al., 2025). According to a study by Amine et al. (2015), the adoption of pounding machines significantly reduced the incidence of injuries among women involved in food processing. Among the various components of such machines, the tuberous food processing chamber is of paramount importance, as it is the primary site of mechanical and thermal interactions during food processing. To optimize the design and performance of these machines, advanced engineering techniques such as Multiphysics Finite Element Method (FEM) based design and thermo-mechanical simulation have been employed in this study. Multiphysics FEM-based design involves the use of computational models that integrate multiple physical phenomena, such as structural mechanics and heat transfer, to simulate the behaviour of complex systems (Patadia & Sweat, 2025; Alotaibi et al., 2025). This approach allows the analyses and optimization of the food processing machines performance under various operating conditions, taking into account the interactions between different physical processes. In the context of tuberous food processing machines analysed in this study, Multiphysics FEM-based design enables the simultaneous consideration of mechanical stresses and equivalent strains, thermal effects, and material properties, leading to more accurate and comprehensive predictions of machine behaviour (Liu, et al., 2025; Zhao et al., 2025). Thermo-mechanical simulation, a subset of Multiphysics analysis, focuses on the coupled effects of thermal and mechanical phenomena. In tuberous food processing machines, this type of simulation is particularly relevant due to the heat generated during the in-chamber food processing and its impact on the structural integrity and performance of the machine components. By incorporating thermo-mechanical simulations into the design process, potential issues related to thermal expansion, material fatigue, and overall machine efficiency can be identified and mitigated (Bassey et al., 2023; Ikpe & Bassey, 2023; Siregar, 2025). The focus on thermal, stress, equivalent, and total deformation analysis on the tuberous food processing chamber is justified by several key factors:

- i. **Critical component:** The tuberous food processing chamber is the primary site of mechanical and thermal interactions during food processing. It experiences high stresses, temperature fluctuations, and deformations, making it the most critical component for ensuring the machine's overall performance and longevity.

- ii. **Stress concentration:** The chamber is subjected to high mechanical stresses during operation, particularly in areas where the geometry changes abruptly. Analysing stress distributions helps identify potential weak points and optimize the chamber design to prevent failure.
- iii. **Equivalent stress analysis:** By examining the equivalent stress (von Mises stress) in the chamber, engineers can assess the likelihood of material yielding and failure under complex loading conditions, ensuring the chamber's durability and safety.
- iv. **Total deformation:** Understanding the total deformation of the chamber under various operating conditions is crucial for maintaining dimensional accuracy, preventing interference between moving parts, and ensuring consistent product quality.
- v. **Material selection:** Thermal and stress analyses provide valuable insights for selecting appropriate materials that can withstand the harsh operating conditions within the chamber while meeting food safety requirements.
- vi. **Design optimization:** By focusing on these analyses, engineers can iteratively refine the chamber design to improve heat dissipation, reduce stress concentrations, and minimize deformations, leading to enhanced performance and longevity of the machine.

By focusing on the thermal, stress, equivalent, and total deformation analysis of the tuberous food processing chamber, more efficient, durable, and safe machines that meet the growing demands of domestic food processing applications can be developed. This approach not only enhances the performance of these machines but also contributes to improved food safety, reduced energy consumption, and increased user satisfaction.

2. Research Methodology

Geometry of the tuberous food processing machine consists of a cylindrical barrel (body) which includes a stainless steel container, polyethylene layer housing the steel container as well as shaft and blades components assembly made from stainless steel. The stainless steel had thermal conductivity of 1.51×10^{-2} W/mm \cdot °C, tensile yield strength of 207 MPa and thermal capacity of 4.8×10^5 mJ/kg \cdot K. However, the polyethylene material had thermal conductivity of 2.8×10^{-4} W/mm \cdot °C, tensile yield strength of 25 MPa and thermal capacity of 2.3×10^6 mJ/kg \cdot K. The polyethylene layer which was found at the base, cover and the cylindrical barrel (body) of the machine served as insulating medium to prevent the escape of heat within the cylindrical vessel.

The CAD models (see Figure 1a-b) developed using ANSYS software showcase an open and a closed design of a tuberous food processing machine. Each model features a stainless steel container equipped with blade components, including a shaft barrel and stainless steel blades for efficient processing. The designs incorporate two layers of polyethylene for insulation, enhancing durability and temperature control. The left model presents an open configuration, while the right model illustrates a closed variant, highlighting versatility in food preparation methods. Details of the model geometry as well as the thermal and mechanical properties are presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Details of the CAD model geometry

Object Name	Material	Length X	Length Y	Length Z	Volume	Mass	Centroid X	Centroid Y	Centroid Z	Moment of Inertia I ₁	Moment of Inertia I ₂	Moment of Inertia I ₃	Nodes	Elements
Blades Component	Stainless Steel	21.911 mm	60. mm	21.911 mm	3383.5 mm ³	3.2143e-003 kg	-138.7 mm	-79.227 mm	67.457 mm	1.1313 kg·mm ²	6.2793e-002 kg·mm ²	1.1313 kg·mm ²	1876	898
		14.847 mm	1.8687 mm	17.539 mm	13.173 mm ³	1.0209e-004 kg	-143.33 mm	-111.12 mm	55.792 mm	2.0046e-003 kg·mm ²	2.0725e-003 kg·mm ²	7.282e-005 kg·mm ²	2168	906
Blades Component	Stainless Steel	15.813 mm	2.0322 mm	18.335 mm	15.426 mm ³	1.1955e-004 kg	-134.1 mm	-74.126 mm	78.997 mm	2.1354e-003 kg·mm ²	2.2312e-003 kg·mm ²	1.0097e-004 kg·mm ²	795	313
		14.847 mm	1.8687 mm	17.539 mm	13.173 mm ³	1.0209e-004 kg	-143.31 mm	-86.126 mm	55.917 mm	2.0046e-003 kg·mm ²	2.0725e-003 kg·mm ²	7.282e-005 kg·mm ²	802	318
Blades Component	Polyethylene	14.847 mm	1.8687 mm	17.539 mm	13.173 mm ³	1.0209e-004 kg	-134.08 mm	-104.12 mm	79.122 mm	2.0046e-003 kg·mm ²	2.0725e-003 kg·mm ²	7.282e-005 kg·mm ²	2159	899
		72.743 mm	20. mm	72.743 mm	10250 mm ³	9.738e-003 kg	-138.7 mm	-111.65 mm	67.459 mm	6.1165 kg·mm ²	11.604 kg·mm ²	6.118 kg·mm ²	5614	2467
Cylindrical Barrel	Stainless Steel	76.749 mm	79. mm	76.749 mm	79188 mm ³	0.6137 kg	-82.644 mm	67.458 mm	67.458 mm	708.21 kg·mm ²	673.91 kg·mm ²	708.21 kg·mm ²	9939	5116
		101.6 mm	25.078 mm	82.749 mm	24476 mm ³	2.3252e-002 kg	-44.517 mm	67.469 mm	67.469 mm	18.142 kg·mm ²	36.161 kg·mm ²	20.707 kg·mm ²	14392	7969
Cover	Polyethylene	82.945 mm	7.4577 mm	82.945 mm	2713.2 mm ³	2.5775e-003 kg	-36.433 mm	-36.433 mm	67.456 mm	0.78583 kg·mm ²	1.5361 kg·mm ²	0.78588 kg·mm ²	31026	15929

Figure 1: CAD model of a tuberous food processing machine

The 3 CAD models depict two variations of a tuberous food processing machine: an open (left) and a closed (right) design. The geometry is defined with a triangular mesh that outlines the cylindrical body and the conical interior surface. The finite element mesh density varies, particularly around the rim and the base. Moreover, triangular meshing is employed, but with an additional lid feature. The mesh is denser at the junctions between components to account for the stresses when the lid is applied, also ensuring a smooth flow of forces across the structure. Both models are designed for efficient simulation of mechanical performance, with the mesh facilitating detailed analysis of structural integrity during operation. Mesh details of the CAD model are presented in Table 2 while the mesh visualization is displayed in Figures 2a-b.

Table 2: Mesh details of the tuberous food processing CAD model

S/N.	Object Name	Mesh Information
1	Physics Preference	Mechanical
2	Type	Triangular mesh
3	Span Angle Center	Medium
4	Initial Size Seed	Part
5	Bounding Box Diagonal	162.11 mm
6	Average Surface Area	430.74 mm ²
7	Minimum Edge Length	0.11524 mm
8	Error Limits	Aggressive Mechanical
9	Target Element Quality	Default (5.e-002)
10	Smoothing	Medium
11	Inflation Option	Smooth Transition
12	Transition Ratio	0.272
13	Maximum Layers	5
14	Growth Rate	1.2
15	Inflation Algorithm	Pre
16	Inflation Element Type	Wedges
17	Rigid Body Behavior	Dimensionally Reduced
18	Sheet Body Method	Quad Dominant
19	Sweep-able Body Method	Sweep
20	Nodes	62052
21	Elements	31533

Figure 2: Mesh visualization of the tuberous food processing CAD model

2.1. Thermal and Structural Analysis

This is the stage where thermal and mechanical loads are applied. The thermal analysis involved solving for temperature distribution, applying flux convergence of $1.e-004$, solver tolerance of $1.e-007$ W/mm, over relaxation of 0.1, Hemicube resolution of 10 as well as maximum iteration of 1000. The thermal boundary conditions included initial temperature of $22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (uniform), internal convection (food heat) including:

- i. Faces: 18
- ii. Coefficient: $5e-4$ W/mm²·°C (500 W/m²·°C)
- iii. Ambient Temperature: $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

However, the external convection (air cooling) included:

- i. Faces: 13
- ii. Coefficient: $1e-5$ W/mm²·°C (10 W/m²·°C)
- iii. Ambient Temperature: $22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

For the static analysis, thermal results was applied as input for von mises stress, equivalent strain and deformation analysis. Details of the static structural loads are presented in Table 3:

Table 3: Details of static structural loads

Object Name	Force	Force 2	Pressure	Fixed Support	Cylindrical Support	Displacement
State	Fully Defined					
Scope						
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection					
Geometry	2 Faces		1 Face			
Definition						
Type	Force		Pressure	Fixed Support	Cylindrical Support	Displacement
Define By	Vector		Normal To			Components
Applied By	Surface Effect					
Magnitude	8. N (ramped)		15. MPa (ramped)			
Loaded Area			Deformed			
Radial					Free	
Axial					Free	
Tangential					Fixed	
Coordinate System						Global Coordinate System
X Component						Free
Y Component						1. mm (ramped)
Z Component						Free
Interpolation Type	Mechanical Results Transfer					
Acceleration	-Y Direction					
X Component	0. mm/s ² (ramped)					
Y Component	-9806.6 mm/s ² (ramped)					
Z Component	0. mm/s ² (ramped)					

3. Results and Discussion

Figures 4a-b depicts two simulation profiles of steady-state thermal temperature distributions of a cylindrical tuberous food processing chamber, modelled as a meshed profile. Figure 4a shows a bottom-heated configuration with a temperature gradient decreasing upward, while Figure 4b illustrates a top-heated profile with the gradient decreasing downward. These distributions suggest heating strategies, such as conduction from the base (see Figure 4a and convection from the top in Figure 4b, which could optimize processing for tuberous foods by ensuring even cooking, sterilization, or drying while minimizing energy loss or material stress. In Figure 4a, the maximum temperature of approximately 80.5°C at the bottom benefits efficient heat transfer for rapid initial processing, implying faster cooking times and better pathogen elimination in denser tuber bases, but risks overheating sensitive materials or uneven doneness if not monitored, potentially leading to nutrient degradation. The minimum of about 51.1°C at the top implies energy conservation by avoiding over-heating unused space, beneficial for cost-effective operations, though it could result in incomplete processing in upper

regions, necessitating stirring or redesign for uniformity. However, in Figure 4b, the peak temperature of about 80°C at the top supports uniform top-down penetration for delicate surface treatments, implying improved flavour retention and reduced scorching in tubers, but may cause thermal fatigue in lid components over time. The minimum of approximately 39.9°C at the bottom benefits safer handling post-processing by quicker cooldown, reducing burn risks, yet implies potential under-processing at the base, which could compromise food safety if microbial activity persists in cooler zones.

Figure 4: Steady-state temperature distribution on tuberos food processing chamber

The ANSYS simulation profiles in Figures 5a-b indicate steady-state total heat flux distributions on a meshed cylindrical chamber for tuberos food processing. Figure 5a presents a higher-flux scenario with a maximum of 0.018579 W/mm² concentrated near the chamber's top/outer edges (red zones), tapering to a near-zero minimum (3.789e-16 W/mm²) at the base/inner walls (blue zones), indicating uneven heat input dominated by localized sources. However, Figure 5b, from a later simulation iteration, exhibits reduced overall heat flux with a maximum of 0.00301 W/mm² (still at outer edges but with a very low intensity) and a minimum of 5.820e-16 W/mm², suggesting improved uniformity and lower energy gradients across the chamber. One of the advantages offered by maximum heat fluxes of 0.018579 W/mm² in Figure 5a and 0.00301 W/mm² in Figure 5b includes targeted heating for efficient processing (faster moisture evaporation in tubers at hotspots), reducing overall energy use by focusing flux where needed. However, the peak values in Figure 5a risk thermal hotspots causing uneven cooking, nutrient degradation, or chamber material stress; whereas, the decline in Figure 5b implies minimized risks, enhancing food quality and equipment longevity as well as reduction in operational costs.

Figure 5: Steady-state total heat flux distribution on tuberous food processing chamber

Figures 6a-b represents ANSYS simulation profiles illustrating the equivalent elastic strain distribution on a meshed cylindrical chamber. This includes a barrel body and internal blade component assembly, designed for tuberous food processing. Figure 6a depicts a high-strain scenario with maximum of 0.081778 mm/mm concentrated at equivalent elastic strain points (red zones, likely at the interface between the dissimilar materials of stainless steel and polyethylene), decreasing to a minimum of $2.526e-9$ mm/mm in low-strain areas (blue zones), indicating potential deformation hotspots from operational forces. Figure 6b indicates a significantly reduced strain profile with a maximum of 0.0001259 mm/mm occurring at the joint between the shaft and the blade root. Judging from the colour distribution, this suggests an optimized design iteration with more uniform distribution and minimal strain concentrations, possibly after material or geometry adjustments. It should be noted that the colour distribution with red implies peak values while blue represent minimum values. These profiles look safe, translating to vibration reduction, better energy transfer for uniform food processing, enhanced durability, with long-term performance and minimal deformation. The plot in Figure 6c quantifies equivalent elastic strain metrics across components, displaying a high maximum value of $8.18E-02$ mm/mm on the cylindrical barrel alongside its average of $1.03E-02$ mm/mm, contrasted with much lower values for the blade component (maximum $1.26E-04$ mm/mm and average $9.15E-06$ mm/mm). This visualization highlights the barrel as the primary stress bearer, likely under greater operational loads, and present design disparities where the blade experiences negligible strain, aiding in targeted material optimizations for the assembly

Figure 6: a. equivalent elastic strain on tuberrous food processing chamber (barrel), and b. equivalent elastic strain on tuberrous food processing blade component assembly

Figure 6c: Plot of maximum and average equivalent elastic strain on tuberrous food processing chamber and blade component assembly

Figures 7a-b represents ANSYS simulations profiles displaying equivalent von Mises stress distributions on a meshed cylindrical chamber assembly for tuberrous food processing, assessing material yielding under static structural and thermal loads. Figure 7a reveals a high-stress configuration with a maximum of 86.856 MPa at critical points (red zones, likely at barrel walls and interfaces between the dissimilar materials of steel and polyethylene), declining to a minimum of 0.00017981 MPa in low-load areas (blue zones), indicating potential stress concentrations from uneven loading. However, Figure 7b shows an optimized scenario with a reduced maximum of 24.268 MPa (concentrated at blade roots or attachments) and the same minimum, suggesting design refinements like geometry changes or material reinforcements for more uniform stress and lower peaks. Von Mises stress predicts ductile material failure by comparing to yield strength; exceeding it leads to plastic deformation, while staying below ensures elastic behaviour (Nasir & Chakma, 2025; Yi & Park, 2025). AISI 304 stainless steel (yield strength of 205-215 MPa) was selected for the food processing chambers

which provides benchmarks for safety. The maximum of 86.856 MPa in Figure 7a implies a safety factor of 2.4-2.5 (yield/86.856) for 304 stainless, acceptable but risking fatigue failure over cycles, potentially causing cracks, leaks, or contamination in hygienic operations. Figure 7b shows maximum blade stress of 24.268 MPa, suggesting optimized blade component assembly profile with a high safety factor (8-12 for 304), reduced failure risks like blade shearing under torque and improved cutting efficiency for tubers. Implications include extended service life and consistent processing but higher cost of production. Figure 7c quantifies von Mises stress metrics, highlighting a dominant maximum of 86.856 MPa on the cylindrical barrel (red bar) with its average at 12.092 MPa, versus lower values on the blade component assembly (maximum 24.268 MPa and average 1.4768 MPa). This emphasizes the barrel as the primary failure-prone element under load, while the blade remains under allowable stress.

Figure 7: a. equivalent von Mises stress on tuberrous food processing chamber (barrel), and b. equivalent von Mises stress on tuberrous food processing blade component assembly

Figure 7c: Plot of maximum and average equivalent von Mises stresses on tuberrous food processing chamber and blade component assembly

Figures 8a-b illustrates ANSYS simulations profiles visualizing total deformation on a meshed cylindrical chamber assembly for tuberous food processing, capturing displacements under static structural loads. Figure 8a shows varied deformation with a maximum of 1.071 mm at key points (red zones, possibly at barrel tops or load interfaces) and a minimum of 0 mm in fixed areas (blue zones), indicating differential expansion or bending. However, Figure 8b depicts a more uniform profile with the same maximum of 1.071 mm (focused on blade elements) but a minimum of 1 mm, suggesting design adjustments for consistent displacement across the structure, reducing gradients. Total deformation measures overall change in geometry; excessive values can cause functional failure like misalignment (Najib et al., 2025; Seid & Amorim, 2025), seal breaches, or accelerated wear, even if below material yield limits, particularly in hygienic food environments where precision is key. Considering AISI 304 stainless steel (Young's modulus 193 GPa, suitable for food contact due to corrosion resistance) that was used in this case, deformation relates to stress via Hooke's law but implies failure if exceeding tolerances of about 0.5-2 mm typical for industrial mixers to avoid vibration or leakage. Maximum total deformation of 1.071 mm in Figure 8a implies potential failure risks such as warping under repeated loads, leading to fatigue cracks or poor sealing, compromising food safety and increasing downtime. On the other hand, similar maximum total deformation in Figure 8b but higher minimum value of 1 mm suggests better load distribution, minimizing failure by enhancing stiffness and performance stability, though it may require thicker materials, thereby increasing costs. Figure 8c represents total deformation metrics in green bars, showing identical maximum values of 1.071 mm for both the cylindrical barrel and blade component, with averages of 0.34583 mm on the barrel and 1.0294 mm on the blade. This highlights the blade as experiencing higher average displacement, likely due to dynamic loads, while the barrel shows greater variability, aiding in identifying components needing reinforcement for balanced assembly performance.

Figure 8: a. total deformation on tuberous food processing chamber (barrel), and b. total deformation on tuberous food processing blade component assembly

Figure 8c: Plot of maximum and average total deformation on tuberous food processing chamber and blade component assembly

4. Conclusion

Based on the ANSYS simulation profiles (heat flux, equivalent elastic strain, von Mises stress, and total deformation) analysed in this study, the design iterations indicate notable enhancements in uniformity and reduction of peaks, but further optimizations can enhance thermal efficiency, structural durability, and overall performance while ensuring food safety and cost-effectiveness. The following suggestions can improve the tuberous food processing design and simulation results:

- i. Enhance Material Selection for the Cylindrical Barrel: Upgrading the barrel material from standard AISI 304 stainless steel to AISI 316L or a high-strength alloy like duplex stainless steel (yield strength >400 MPa) to better withstand the maximum elastic strain of 8.18 mm/mm in Figure 6a and von Mises stress of 86.856 MPa in Figure 7a. The barrel bears the brunt of stress and strain as shown on the profiles, risking fatigue failure or cracking under cyclic loads from tuber processing. This upgrade can increase the safety factor (from 2.4 to >4), reduce deformation variability (1.071 mm in Figures 8a-b), and minimize the risk of leaks or contamination, improving longevity and hygiene without significantly altering heat flux distribution.
- ii. Optimize Geometry for Uniform Load and Heat Distribution: Incorporation of internal ribs, fillets at stress concentrations, or a tapered barrel design. In addition, integration of baffles or helical blades can also promote even heat flow and mixing. High heat flux hotspots in Figure 5a (0.018579 W/mm²) and stress concentrations in both iterations indicate uneven loading, leading to potential thermal degradation of tubers or material warping (deformation up to 1.071 mm in Figures 8a-b). These changes, as partially achieved in Figure 5b with reduced flux and stress (to 24 MPa in Figure 7b), would further minimize gradients, enhance energy efficiency, and ensure consistent processing quality, reducing nutrient loss in foods like potatoes.
- iii. Improve Blade Component Reinforcement and Attachment: Thicken blade roots or use bolted/welded reinforcements with damping materials. Moreover, simulate dynamic loads via harmonic analysis in ANSYS to address higher average deformation on blades in Figure 8c (1.0294 mm). While maximum stress (24.268 MPa) transition to the blades in Figure (b), implying better barrel relief, the persistent deformation suggests vibration

risks during operation, potentially causing blade fatigue or inefficient grinding. Reinforcements would boost torsional resistance, lower strain (from 0.0001259 mm/mm in Figure 6b, and enhance overall assembly performance, leading to smoother operation, reduced maintenance, and higher throughput.

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